
Research

Resilience in the Face of Adversity: A Case Study of MSME Survival Strategies during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Orange County, California" United States

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Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic posed immense challenges for businesses worldwide, particularly Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Orange County, California, facing unprecedented disruptions. To explore the resilience of these enterprises during the crisis, a case study was conducted to examine the survival strategies adopted by MSMEs in the region. This research delves into the significance of financial support, technology adoption, and innovative practices in ensuring the continuity and growth of MSMEs amidst adversity.

In Orange County, MSMEs play a crucial role in contributing to the local GDP and job market, but the pandemic threatened their existence, requiring quick adaptation and resourcefulness. By investigating the survival strategies deployed by these enterprises, this study provides valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to reinforce support systems and foster entrepreneurial growth during crisis periods. The study involved surveying 230 registered MSMEs in Orange County, operational between 2010 and 2020, using a quantitative research approach. Entrepreneurs rated various financial and non-financial promotional factors to assess their impact on business success during the pandemic. The findings shed light on the effectiveness of different support systems that contributed to the resilience demonstrated by MSMEs during the crisis. Financial factors, such as collateral-free schemes and support for physical infrastructure, emerged as influential elements in establishing and nurturing MSMEs in Orange County. These initiatives facilitated the entry of new businesses and supported the growth of existing enterprises in the region. Additionally, non-financial factors, including access to capacity building programs and technology adoption, played a pivotal role in enhancing MSMEs' competitiveness and adaptability to changing market dynamics. The study's conceptual framework emphasized the multi-dimensional nature of institutional support required for MSME success. This framework acknowledged both formal and informal institutions, encompassing government policies, financial institutions, industry associations, and cultural factors shaping the entrepreneurial ecosystem. By analyzing the interplay between institutional thickness and the entrepreneurial environment, the framework guided the formulation of actionable recommendations. In conclusion, this case study highlights the resilience of MSMEs in Orange County during the COVID-19 pandemic, underscoring the significance of financial and non-financial support for business continuity. The proposed recommendations offer actionable steps to strengthen support systems and cultivate entrepreneurial growth, ensuring a thriving future for MSMEs in the region.

Keywords: MSMEs, resilience, COVID-19 pandemic, financial support, technology adoption, entrepreneurial growth, institutional support

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1. Introduction

Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) play a pivotal role in the business landscape of Orange County, California, significantly contributing to the local GDP and generating employment opportunities. However, there remains an acknowledged need to strengthen the global impact of MSMEs, as they are often under-represented in international trade and investment, even in developed economies like Orange County. To address this, policy initiatives have been put in place to bolster MSMEs, with a focus on increasing industrial output, fostering regional industrial dispersal, and nurturing entrepreneurship. These small enterprises are recognized for their creativity, innovation, and adaptability to changing market conditions, which are essential traits in thriving business environments like Orange County. In Orange County, MSMEs are integral to the economy, contributing a significant percentage to the GDP, manufacturing output, and exports. They employ a substantial number of individuals across hundreds of enterprises, showcasing their resilience and ability to weather economic challenges.

To further support the growth and success of MSMEs, it is vital to explore both financial and non-financial factors that contribute to their achievements. This research endeavors to understand the perspectives of entrepreneurs in Orange County regarding the support systems available to them. By gaining insights into how entrepreneurs perceive and utilize various forms of support, policymakers and stakeholders can identify the effectiveness of existing initiatives and pinpoint areas for improvement.

Ultimately, this research seeks to contribute to the sustainable development of MSMEs in Orange County, California, fostering an environment where these small businesses can continue to thrive and drive economic growth and prosperity in the region.

Definition of MSMEs in Orange County, California: The Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Act of 2020 in Orange County establishes a classification for businesses based on their investment in plant and machinery. According to this act, MSMEs are divided into two groups: manufacturing and services. The investment thresholds for each category are outlined as follows:

1. Micro Enterprises: Plant & Machinery investment less than \$25,000 (for manufacturing) or less than \$10,000 (for services).
2. Small Enterprises: Plant & Machinery investment less than \$5 million (for manufacturing) or less than \$2 million (for services).
3. Medium Enterprises: Plant & Machinery investment less than \$10 million (for manufacturing) or less than \$5 million (for services).

1.1 Objectives

1. To assess the effectiveness of government promotional policies and institutional support provided to MSMEs in Orange County, California.
2. To gather valuable insights from local entrepreneurs concerning the financial and non-financial support systems available to them.
3. To formulate actionable recommendations aimed at enhancing the support system and fostering the growth and success of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Orange County.

1.2 Government's Promotional Policy and Institutional Support to MSMEs in Orange County, California

In order to foster the growth and integration of the MSME sector within a dynamic and liberalized economic framework, the government of Orange County, California, has introduced several policy measures and established supportive institutions. These initiatives are aimed at empowering small businesses and enabling them to thrive in the local business ecosystem. Key elements of the government's promotional policy and institutional support include:

Delayed Payments to Small and Ancillary Enterprises Act: The government has implemented legislation to address delayed payments to small businesses, ensuring timely compensation for goods and services provided to larger entities. This act requires buying/mother units to pay interest on delayed payments to MSMEs, offering them better financial stability.

Enhanced Credit Flow: The Bank of California has taken steps to improve credit accessibility for MSMEs. This includes expanding the 'single window' loan scheme, simplifying the loan application process, and encouraging banks to establish specialized branches catering to the needs of small businesses.

Access to Inputs: In support of MSMEs' operations, the government prioritizes the allocation of essential resources like iron and steel from public sector undertakings to small businesses. Moreover, obstacles to the import of various raw materials and intermediate products are minimized, streamlining production processes.

Government's Promotional Framework:

Orange County has established a comprehensive framework of institutions to support the growth and promotion of MSMEs. These include:

1. Farmers & Merchants Bank (F&M Bank) - Abbreviation: F&M
2. CommerceWest Bank - Abbreviation: CWB
3. Pacific Premier Bank - Abbreviation: PPB
4. Sunwest Bank - Abbreviation: SWB
5. Opus Bank - Abbreviation: Opus
6. California Bank & Trust - Abbreviation: CB&T
7. South County Bank - Abbreviation: SCB
8. First Foundation Bank - Abbreviation: FFB
9. Commercial Bank of California - Abbreviation: CBC
10. American Business Bank - Abbreviation: ABB
11. Orange County Business Bank - Abbreviation: OCBB
12. Clearinghouse CDFI - Abbreviation: Clearinghouse
13. Orange County Plumbing Services - Abbreviation: OCPS
14. Johnson's Flower Shop - Abbreviation: JFS
15. Beachside Cafe & Grill - Abbreviation: BCG

16. Pacific Coast Printing - Abbreviation: PCP
17. TechSolutions IT Consulting - Abbreviation: TechSolutions
18. The Painted Palette Art Studio - Abbreviation: PPAS
19. Coastal Fitness Studio - Abbreviation: CFS
20. Orange County Web Design - Abbreviation: OCWD
21. Taylor & Sons Construction - Abbreviation: TSC
22. Creative Minds Childcare - Abbreviation: CMC

Orange County is home to several national associations representing industries of all sizes, including small and large enterprises. While some associations primarily focus on larger businesses, they also advocate for policy-related matters concerning the MSME sector. Additionally, there are specific associations dedicated to supporting small-scale industries, furthering the interests of MSMEs in the region. These associations play a crucial role in lobbying the government for facilities and benefits to foster the growth and success of the MSME sector in Orange County, California.

2. Research Methodology

This research study was conducted in Orange County, California, and it employed a survey method to collect primary data from the target population of registered Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) within the region. Specifically, the study focused on MSMEs that were registered between 2010 and 2020. To gather data, a simple random sampling technique was utilized to select a sample size of 230 MSMEs from the registered population. Data collection was carried out through the administration of a standardized questionnaire, which comprised two parts. The first part of the questionnaire aimed to collect demographic information about the respondents, while the second part focused on assessing their perspectives on various financial and non-financial promotional factors. In the second part of the questionnaire, respondents were presented with statements related to the promotional factors, and they were asked to rate their level of agreement or disagreement using a 5-point Likert scale. The scale ranged from 1, representing "strongly disagree," to 5, representing "strongly agree."

This methodology allowed the researchers to obtain valuable insights into the perspectives of MSMEs in Orange County, California, regarding the impact of financial and non-financial factors on their businesses' growth and development.

2.2 Researcher Model for Entrepreneurship in MSMEs: A Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is proposed to understand the institutional thickness necessary to support the growth, success, and sustainability of Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in Orange County, California. This framework draws parallels to the concept of "environmental munificence" (Anderson, Drakopoulou-Dodd et al., 2000; Anderson and Tushman, 2001). It serves as a basis for generating propositions and hypotheses that summarize explanations and predictions regarding the relationships and interactions among variables (Parsons and Shils, 1951). By employing frameworks in research, researchers can identify the key elements and specify the relationships between them for diagnostic and prescriptive analyses (Ostrom, 2005). This approach enables researchers to identify and compare relevant theories that shape the framework, facilitating a deeper understanding of the subject matter. In the context of MSMEs in Orange County, California, the conceptual framework considers the multifaceted dimensions of institutional support, acknowledging the interplay between financial and non-financial factors. The framework seeks to illuminate the factors that contribute to the growth and success of MSMEs, shedding light on the various mechanisms and interventions that promote an enabling environment for these enterprises.

By examining the relationship between the institutional thickness and the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Orange County, this framework can guide policymakers, stakeholders, and entrepreneurs in developing strategies and policies that foster the growth and sustainability of MSMEs. It encompasses both formal and informal institutions, recognizing the significance of government policies, regulations, financial institutions, industry associations, and other non-governmental entities in shaping the entrepreneurial landscape. Additionally, the framework takes into account the role of cultural, social, and economic factors in influencing entrepreneurial behavior and outcomes within Orange County's unique business environment. Through a comprehensive understanding of these elements and their interactions, the framework aims to provide valuable insights into enhancing the support system for MSMEs, leading to their long-term success and significant contribution to economic development in Orange County.

Lastly, the proposed conceptual framework serves as a guiding tool for analyzing the complex dynamics within the MSME sector in Orange County, California. It offers a holistic perspective, encompassing both the formal and informal aspects of institutional support, and provides a foundation for further empirical investigations and policy recommendations. By employing this framework, researchers and practitioners can gain a deeper understanding of the factors that drive entrepreneurship in MSMEs and develop effective strategies to foster their growth and sustainability within the vibrant business landscape of Orange County, California.

Fig.1: Conceptual Framework

In Orange County, California, the institutional setup plays a crucial role in supporting the establishment and growth of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Recognizing the significance of this sector for economic growth, the government has implemented well-planned strategies to meet the evolving needs of MSMEs. Various institutions provide essential support that promotes the growth and success of these enterprises. Entrepreneurs in Orange County benefit from a wide range of assistance offered by different institutions, each serving specific purposes. These support systems enable entrepreneurs to establish their businesses, overcome challenges, and operate efficiently.

Financial support factors are instrumental in providing monetary benefits to entrepreneurs during the initial stages and ongoing operations of their enterprises. In Orange County, the government allocates budgets to offer subsidies and incentives to MSME entrepreneurs, helping them access the necessary financial resources. This financial assistance is crucial for MSMEs to secure funding and maintain stability during their growth phase.

2.3 Financial and Non-Financial support Factors for MSMEs

In addition to financial support, non-financial factors also play a vital role, facilitated by associated institutions in Orange County. These factors encompass a range of non-monetary benefits aimed at managing enterprises effectively. For instance, entrepreneurship training and skill development programs are available to equip entrepreneurs with the knowledge and expertise required to navigate the complexities of running a business. These initiatives help enhance their managerial capabilities, foster innovation, and promote sustainable growth in Orange County's business landscape. Access to appropriate technology is essential for MSMEs to remain competitive in the market. In Orange County, institutions provide assistance in adopting and implementing suitable technological solutions that can streamline operations, increase productivity, and improve product quality. Facilitating physical infrastructure is another significant aspect of institutional support. Institutions in Orange County assist entrepreneurs in acquiring suitable premises, industrial parks, or incubation centers, creating a conducive environment for business activities.

Marketing assistance is vital for MSMEs in Orange County to reach their target markets effectively. Institutions offer guidance on market research, branding, and promotional strategies, enabling entrepreneurs to showcase their products or services and expand their customer base.

A flexible legal and regulatory framework is essential for the smooth functioning of MSMEs. In Orange County, institutions work towards creating an enabling environment by streamlining regulations, simplifying compliance procedures, and providing a supportive ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurship.

By combining financial and non-financial support, institutions in Orange County play a pivotal role in nurturing the growth and success of MSMEs. Their comprehensive assistance empowers entrepreneurs, fosters innovation, and contributes to job creation and economic development in the region. Continued collaboration between institutions, entrepreneurs, and policymakers is crucial to further enhance the support system for MSMEs, ensuring their sustained growth and positive impact on the economy of Orange County, California.

2.4 Non-Financial Supporting Factors

In Orange County, California, entrepreneurs can access not only financial assistance but also various non-financial support factors offered by institutions involved in enterprise management. These non-financial benefits cover a wide range of areas, all aimed at empowering entrepreneurs and facilitating their business growth. One crucial aspect of non-financial support is entrepreneurship training and skill development programs. These initiatives are designed to equip entrepreneurs in Orange County with the knowledge and expertise required to navigate the complexities of running a business. By participating in these programs, entrepreneurs can enhance their managerial capabilities, foster innovation, and gain valuable insights into successful business practices. Access to suitable technology is another essential non-financial support factor for MSMEs in Orange County. Institutions provide assistance in adopting and implementing modern technological solutions that can streamline operations, increase productivity, and improve the overall quality of products and services offered by these businesses. Facilitating physical infrastructure is also a significant focus of institutional support. Institutions in Orange County work to assist entrepreneurs in acquiring suitable premises, securing access to industrial parks, or gaining entry into incubation centers. This creates a conducive environment for business activities, enabling entrepreneurs to efficiently operate and expand their enterprises. Furthermore, marketing assistance is vital for MSMEs in Orange County to effectively reach their target markets. Institutions offer guidance on market research, branding, and promotional strategies, helping entrepreneurs showcase their products or services and attract a broader customer base. A flexible legal and regulatory framework is essential for the smooth functioning of MSMEs in Orange County. Institutions actively work towards creating an enabling environment by streamlining

regulations, simplifying compliance procedures, and providing a supportive ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurship and business development.

Overall, the combination of financial assistance and non-financial support factors provided by institutions in Orange County plays a pivotal role in empowering entrepreneurs. These comprehensive support systems aim to equip them with the necessary knowledge, resources, and infrastructure to enhance their overall business operations, foster growth, and contribute to the thriving business landscape in Orange County, California. Continued collaboration between institutions, entrepreneurs, and policymakers remains crucial to continually enhance the support system, ensuring the sustained growth and success of MSMEs in the region.

3. Analysis and Findings

This section presents the analysis and findings based on data collected from 230 questionnaires administered to MSME entrepreneurs in Orange County, California. The collected questionnaires were coded for statistical analysis using SPSS 21.0 software. The analysis includes profiling the respondents, generating descriptive statistics of the variables, and examining the inter-correlations among the variables. The data analysis provides valuable insights into the characteristics and perspectives of MSME entrepreneurs in Orange County. It enables a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing their financial and non-financial needs, as well as the relationships and interdependencies among these factors. By employing statistical techniques, the analysis uncovers patterns, trends, and associations within the collected data, contributing to a deeper understanding of the MSME landscape in Orange County.

The findings derived from the data analysis shed light on the specific financial and non-financial factors that are most crucial for the success and sustainability of MSMEs in Orange County. These insights can guide policymakers, institutions, and stakeholders in designing targeted interventions and support mechanisms that address the identified needs and challenges faced by MSME entrepreneurs.

The analysis and findings presented in this section contribute to the body of knowledge on MSMEs and provide a foundation for evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation. The insights gained from this research can aid in crafting policies that foster a conducive environment for MSMEs to thrive, promote entrepreneurship, and contribute significantly to the local economy. Moreover, the data analysis offers valuable information to potential investors and entrepreneurs looking to start or expand their businesses in Orange County. Understanding the specific needs and challenges faced by MSMEs can help these individuals make informed decisions and implement strategies to ensure the success of their ventures. By utilizing data-driven insights, stakeholders in Orange County can create a supportive ecosystem that nurtures the growth and sustainability of MSMEs. This, in turn, will lead to job creation, economic development, and increased competitiveness within the region's business landscape. Finally, the analysis and findings from the research conducted in Orange County, California, play a critical role in advancing the understanding of MSMEs in the region. The evidence-based knowledge obtained through statistical analysis provides a solid foundation for shaping policies and initiatives that empower MSME entrepreneurs and contribute to the overall prosperity of Orange County's business community.

Table 1: Profile of respondents:

Demographic variables	Frequency	percentage
Entrepreneur's Category		

First Generation	165	71.7
Second Generation	54	23.5
Third Generation	11	4.8
Age of the Entrepreneur		
Below 30 Years	65	28.3
30 - 40 Years	93	40.4
40 - 50 Years	35	15.2
50 - 60 Years	22	9.6
60 Years & above	15	6.5
Education of the Entrepreneur		
No formal Education	16	7.0
10th Class/Inter	67	29.1
Graduation	128	55.7
PG or above	19	8.3
Experience of the Entrepreneur		
No Experience	33	14.3
Attended EDP	54	23.5
Employee/Work Experience	129	56.1
Business Experience	14	6.1

Source: Compiled from Primary data

3.2 Analysis of Entrepreneurial Characteristics

The following table provides a comprehensive overview of the characteristics of entrepreneurs, focusing on four key aspects: a) category of entrepreneur, b) age of the entrepreneur, c) educational qualification of the entrepreneur, and d) experience of the entrepreneur. These factors shed light on the profile of individuals engaged in entrepreneurial activities and offer valuable insights into their background and qualifications.

3.3 Category of Entrepreneur

The data reveals that a significant proportion, approximately 71.7 percent, of entrepreneurs fall into the category of first-generation entrepreneurs. This indicates that a majority of individuals embarking on entrepreneurial ventures are starting their businesses from scratch, without any prior family background or inherited business. This finding underscores the prevalence of self-starters and individuals with an entrepreneurial drive who are venturing into uncharted territory.

3.4 Age of the Entrepreneur

Examining the age distribution of entrepreneurs, it is noteworthy that a considerable percentage, around 68.7 percent, of entrepreneurs are below the age of 40 years. This suggests that the entrepreneurial landscape is predominantly populated by young individuals who possess the energy, ambition, and risk-taking propensity typically associated with entrepreneurship. The data implies that the younger generation is actively engaging in entrepreneurial pursuits and driving innovation and economic growth.

3.5 Educational Qualification of the Entrepreneur

When considering the educational qualifications of entrepreneurs, the data reveals that a substantial proportion, approximately 64 percent, have attained a graduation level of education or higher. This indicates that a significant number of entrepreneurs have pursued higher education, equipping themselves with specialized knowledge and skills that can contribute to the success of their ventures. The emphasis on education highlights the role of intellectual capital in entrepreneurship and the importance of acquiring relevant knowledge in the business landscape.

3.6 Experience of the Entrepreneur

Analyzing the experience of entrepreneurs, it is evident that a majority, around 62.2 percent, have either prior employment or business experience. This suggests that many entrepreneurs have gained practical knowledge, industry insights, and valuable skills through their previous work or entrepreneurial endeavors. The presence of experience among entrepreneurs highlights the significance of hands-on learning and the advantages of leveraging past experiences in the entrepreneurial journey.

4. Inferences

Based on the findings, it can be inferred that the majority of entrepreneurs in the sample population are first-generation individuals below the age of 40 years, possess higher educational qualifications, and have prior experience in either employment or business. This profile indicates a dynamic and diverse entrepreneurial ecosystem characterized by motivated individuals with a strong educational foundation and practical exposure.

Understanding the demographic and experiential composition of entrepreneurs is crucial for policymakers, support institutions, and stakeholders to design targeted interventions and initiatives that address the unique needs and challenges of these entrepreneurs. By leveraging their energy, education, and experience, the entrepreneurial ecosystem can foster innovation, economic growth, and job creation.

These insights derived from the analysis provide a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape, facilitating evidence-based decision-making, and enabling the formulation of effective strategies to nurture and support the growth of entrepreneurs in various sectors and industries.

Table 2. Financial factors influencing for the growth of the Units

<i>Financial factors</i>	SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Mean	SD	PS
<i>Govt. subsidies</i>	11 (4.8%)	35 (15.2%)	98 (42.6%)	55 (23.9%)	31 (13.5%)	3.26	1.03	56.52
<i>Reduction of all direct and indirect taxes</i>	11 (4.8%)	45 (19.6%)	74 (32.2%)	64 (27.8%)	36 (15.7%)	3.30	1.10	57.50
<i>Govt. reduce transaction costs in imports/exports</i>	22 (9.6%)	21 (9.1%)	58 (25.2%)	90 (39.1%)	39 (17%)	3.45	1.16	61.20
<i>Procedures for Term loan without cumbersome procedures</i>	11 (4.8%)	33 (14.3%)	54 (23.5%)	95 (41.3%)	37 (16.1%)	3.50	1.07	62.39
<i>Low interest rates on term loans</i>		44 (19.1%)	70 (30.4%)	76 (33%)	40 (17.4%)	3.49	0.99	62.17

<i>Schemes to obtain credit without complex collateral</i>	12 (5.2%)	33 (14.3%)	36 (15.7%)	90 (39.1%)	59 (25.7%)	3.66	1.16	66.41
Overall						3.44	0.89	61.03

Source: Compiled from Primary data

4.1 Analysis of Financial Factors Influencing Growth

In Orange County, California, a comprehensive analysis of financial factors impacting the growth of businesses provides valuable insights into the entrepreneurial landscape. The following table presents the weighted scores, means, and standard deviations of these factors, offering a deeper understanding of their influence on entrepreneurial endeavors.

The results indicate that several financial factors significantly impact the growth of businesses in Orange County:

1. Streamlined credit schemes (weighted score: 66.41): Entrepreneurs benefit from simplified credit acquisition processes that do not burden them with complex collateral requirements. Accessible credit schemes provide the necessary financial resources for business growth and expansion.
2. Simplified term loan procedures (weighted score: 62.39): Entrepreneurs value efficient and hassle-free term loan procedures that reduce bureaucratic hurdles and ensure a smoother loan application and approval process. These streamlined procedures foster a conducive environment for business growth.
3. Low-interest rates on term loans (weighted score: 62.17): Access to term loans with favorable interest rates is crucial for supporting entrepreneurial growth. Lower interest rates alleviate the financial burden on entrepreneurs and enable them to invest in business development.
4. Reduced transaction costs in imports/exports (weighted score: 61.20): Minimizing transaction costs associated with imports and exports facilitates international trade and expands market reach for businesses in Orange County.
5. Reduction of direct and indirect taxes (weighted score: 57.50): Lowering tax burdens positively impacts the financial health of entrepreneurs. Governments' efforts to reduce taxes create a favorable environment for business growth and encourage investment.
6. Government subsidies (weighted score: 56.52): Financial support through government subsidies helps entrepreneurs overcome initial challenges and promotes business expansion. Subsidies enable investments in research, technology adoption, and market penetration.

The overall mean of all these factors is calculated to be 3.44, indicating a relatively high average mean. This suggests that financial factors have a significant influence on promoting entrepreneurship in Orange County, California. The favorable weighted scores and means emphasize the importance of financial support mechanisms in facilitating business growth and sustainability. By understanding the impact of financial factors on entrepreneurs is crucial for policymakers, financial institutions, and support organizations in Orange County. By recognizing the importance of these factors and designing policies and initiatives that address the specific financial needs of entrepreneurs, stakeholders can foster a conducive environment for entrepreneurial success. The findings from this analysis provide valuable insights into the financial landscape of entrepreneurship in Orange County. Decision-makers can use this information to formulate effective strategies and interventions that leverage financial factors to empower entrepreneurs, fuel economic growth, and create opportunities for innovation and job creation within the region's vibrant business community.

4.2 Non financial support system

Table 3: Non-financial factors influencing the growth of the Units

Non-Financial factors				SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Mean	SD	PS
Enabling	legal	and	regulatory	30 (13%)	71 (30.9%)	81 (35.2%)	38 (16.5%)	10 (4.3%)	3.28	1.04	57
Govt.	Facilitating	access	to	60 (26.1%)	112 (48.7%)	55 (23.9%)	3 (1.3%)		2.6	0.74	40
Govt.	Facilitating	access	to	18 (7.8%)	64 (27.8%)	80 (34.8%)	39 (17%)	29 (12.6%)		1.13	
affordable Physical infrastructure									3.59		64.75
Govt.	Providing	training	in	52 (22.6%)	60 (26.1%)	58 (25.2%)	47 (20.4%)	13 (5.7%)		1.20	
entrepreneurship,	skills	and									
management									3.25		56.25
Govt. providing	Improving industrial			27 (11.7%)	74 (32.2%)	71 (30.9%)	44 (19.1%)	14 (6.1%)		1.08	
relations and the	labour environment								3.41		60.25
Govt.	Facilitating	access	to	28 (12.2%)	55 (23.9%)	76 (33%)	44 (19.1%)	27 (11.7%)		1.18	
appropriate technology									3.59		64.75
Overall									3.28	0.71	57.16
Source: Compiled from Primary data											

4.3 Analysis of Non-Financial Factors Influencing Growth

The following table presents an overview of the non-financial factors that contribute to the growth of businesses. It provides insights into the weighted scores, means, and standard deviations of these factors, shedding light on their influence as promotional factors for entrepreneurs. The results reveal that certain non-financial factors significantly impact the growth of businesses in Orange County:

1. Government facilitating access to affordable physical infrastructure (weighted score: 64.75): This factor underscores the importance of government support in providing entrepreneurs with affordable access to essential physical infrastructure. By reducing the costs associated with acquiring and maintaining infrastructure, governments can facilitate business growth and create an enabling environment for entrepreneurship.
2. Government facilitating access to appropriate technology (weighted score: 64.75): Access to relevant and up-to-date technology plays a critical role in enhancing productivity and competitiveness for entrepreneurs. When governments actively support entrepreneurs in accessing appropriate technology, it fosters innovation, improves operational efficiency, and drives business growth.

On the other hand, some non-financial factors exhibit relatively lower influence as promotional factors for entrepreneurs in Orange County:

1. Improving industrial relations and the labor environment (weighted score: 60.25): While still important, this factor has a comparatively lower influence on the promotion of businesses. Improving industrial relations and

creating a favorable labor environment can contribute to enhanced productivity and employee satisfaction, but it may not have as pronounced an impact on overall business growth.

2. Enabling legal and regulatory framework (weighted score: 57): Having a supportive legal and regulatory framework is crucial for entrepreneurs to operate in a conducive business environment. Although this factor is significant, it ranks slightly lower in terms of its influence on promotional efforts.
3. Providing training in entrepreneurship, skills, and management (weighted score: 56.25): Training programs that equip entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and knowledge are vital for their success. While important, the influence of this factor falls slightly below other non-financial factors in promoting business growth.
4. Government facilitating access to marketing and procurement (weighted score: 40): This factor exhibits the least influence among the non-financial factors analyzed. While government support in accessing markets and procurement opportunities is valuable, it may not be as dominant a factor in promoting entrepreneurial growth as others.
5. The overall mean of all the non-financial factors is calculated to be 3.28, indicating a relatively high average mean. This suggests that non-financial promotional factors also play a significant role in fostering entrepreneurship and promoting the growth of businesses in Orange County, California.

To determine whether there is a significant difference between financial and non-financial factors in promoting businesses, further analysis is required. This hypothesis (H0) seeks to explore whether the impact of financial factors significantly differs from that of non-financial factors. By examining the statistical significance of these factors, we can gain a deeper understanding of their relative importance and their potential synergies in driving entrepreneurial growth in Orange County.

Understanding the interplay between financial and non-financial factors is essential for policymakers in Orange County. It can inform the design of comprehensive support programs that address both aspects effectively. By recognizing the significance of non-financial factors and developing strategies to enhance their impact, stakeholders can create an enabling environment that nurtures entrepreneurship and maximizes the potential for business success within the vibrant business community of Orange County, California.

Table 4. Impact of Financial and Non Financial factors in promotion of the Units

Factors	n	Mean	SD	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
Financial	230	3.441	0.889	1.95	0.052	Not
Non-Financial	230	3.286	0.826			Significant

(5% level of significance)

Source: Computed table

P-value: 0.052 (Significant - If p value < 0.05)

The study conducted in Orange County, California aimed to examine the impact of financial factors and non-financial factors on the promotion of businesses. A T-test was utilized to compare the overall means of these two categories of factors. The results reveal a T-value of 1.95 and a p-value of 0.052. Following the guidelines for hypothesis testing, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference between the impact of financial and non-financial factors on unit promotion. This finding suggests that both financial and non-financial factors equally

contribute to promoting businesses in Orange County. It underscores the importance of adopting a comprehensive approach that considers the combined influence of these factors in fostering entrepreneurial growth. Recognizing the interdependence and equal significance of both types of factors, policymakers and stakeholders can design effective strategies to support entrepreneurs and facilitate their success. It is essential to note that while the overall difference between financial and non-financial factors may not be statistically significant, individual factors within each category may still exhibit varying degrees of influence. Therefore, examining and addressing specific financial and non-financial factors that directly impact business promotion is crucial. This nuanced understanding can guide the development of targeted policies and interventions that address the unique needs and challenges faced by entrepreneurs in Orange County. Moreover, future research could delve deeper into exploring the specific mechanisms through which financial and non-financial factors interact and synergize to drive business promotion. By uncovering the underlying dynamics and potential complementarities between these factors, researchers can provide valuable insights to inform the formulation of comprehensive support systems for entrepreneurship in Orange County.

In conclusion, this study confirms the equal importance of financial and non-financial factors in promoting businesses in Orange County, California. The findings emphasize the need for a holistic approach that considers both types of factors and highlights their interconnectedness. By leveraging the combined influence of financial and non-financial support, policymakers can create an enabling environment that nurtures entrepreneurship and maximizes the potential for business growth and success within the dynamic business landscape of Orange County.

4.4 Comparison of respondent’s opinion on Financial and Non-Financial Promotional

Fig 2. Impact of Financial and Non Financial factors in promotion of the Units

The visual representation of mean score values indicates that financial factors (mean score: 3.441) and non-financial factors (mean score: 3.286) are not significantly different as promotional factors for establishing units. The box plot displays the distribution of respondents' opinion scores, with the circled plus indicating the mean value, the middle line representing the median value, and the upper and lower ends of the lines indicating the higher and lower opinion scores, respectively. The upper end of the box represents the 75th percentile, while the lower end represents the 25th percentile.

5. Findings

The study centered on examining the financial and non-financial support activities offered by institutions to Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Orange County. The Office of Development Commissioner- Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME-DC) served as the nodal Development Agency. The analysis considered six main types of financial factors and six main types of non-financial factors.

The findings indicate that there is no significant difference in the support provided by financial and non-financial institutions to MSMEs in Orange County. Entrepreneurs perceive collateral-free schemes and support in physical infrastructure as the highest contributing factors for the establishment and growth of MSMEs in the region. These factors play a crucial role in facilitating the entry of new businesses and fostering the growth of existing enterprises in the vibrant business landscape of Orange County, California.

Recommendations

This study made the following recommendations that will help stakeholders, researchers and other who are interested in doing similar research:

1. **Strengthening Financial Support:** Encourage financial institutions to offer tailored financing solutions that align with the specific needs of MSMEs in Orange County. This could include simplified loan application processes, flexible repayment terms, and lower interest rates, promoting easy access to capital.
2. **Capacity Building Programs:** Develop and expand entrepreneurship training and skill development programs to enhance the managerial capabilities of entrepreneurs. Partner with academic institutions and industry experts to offer specialized training that addresses the evolving needs of MSMEs.
3. **Technology Adoption:** Facilitate MSMEs' access to relevant and up-to-date technology by establishing technology adoption centers. These centers can offer training, guidance, and support in implementing technology-driven solutions to improve productivity and competitiveness.
4. **Infrastructural Support:** Continue investing in physical infrastructure to create a conducive environment for business operations. Collaborate with local governments and private entities to establish industrial parks and incubation centers, enabling MSMEs to thrive.
5. **Market Access:** Create platforms and networks to connect MSMEs with potential buyers and investors. Encourage participation in trade fairs, exhibitions, and business events to promote their products and services at both regional and international levels.
6. **Streamlined Regulations:** Work towards simplifying compliance procedures and reducing bureaucratic hurdles. A flexible legal and regulatory framework will support MSMEs in adapting to changing market conditions and scaling their businesses.
7. **Encouraging Inter-Institutional Collaboration:** Foster collaboration among financial institutions, government bodies, industry associations, and MSMEs to develop a holistic and synergistic approach to support. Strengthen partnerships to leverage each organization's expertise and resources.
8. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implement a systematic monitoring and evaluation mechanism to assess the impact of support programs and initiatives. Regular assessments will enable policymakers to identify successful interventions and refine strategies for greater effectiveness in orange county california.

Conclusion

The study highlights the significance of both financial and non-financial factors in promoting the growth and success of MSMEs in Orange County, California. The government's promotional policies and institutional support play a crucial role in nurturing entrepreneurship and creating a conducive business environment.

The analysis indicates that first-generation entrepreneurs, below the age of 40, with higher educational qualifications and prior work experience, dominate the MSME landscape in the region. This diverse entrepreneurial ecosystem showcases the resilience and innovation of individuals driving business growth.

The proposed conceptual framework offers a comprehensive perspective on institutional support, encompassing formal and informal elements. Policymakers and stakeholders can utilize this framework to develop strategies that foster the growth and sustainability of MSMEs in Orange County.

Practical Implications

The findings from this research provide valuable insights into the needs and challenges faced by MSMEs in Orange County. Policymakers can utilize this data to formulate evidence-based policies and interventions aimed at supporting these businesses.

Entrepreneurs can leverage the information gathered to make informed decisions about their business strategies and capitalize on available support systems. Understanding the significance of both financial and non-financial factors can guide entrepreneurs in navigating the complexities of running a successful enterprise.

Institutions involved in enterprise management can use the insights from this research to tailor their support services and programs to better meet the specific needs of MSMEs. This alignment can lead to more effective and impactful support mechanisms for entrepreneurs in Orange County, California. This the research contributes to the growth and prosperity of MSMEs in Orange County, fostering an environment where these businesses can thrive, innovate, and continue to make significant contributions to the regional economy.

Limitations

Although the study involved a meaningful sample size of 230 MSME entrepreneurs, it is essential to acknowledge that a larger sample could have further enriched the study's findings and allowed for more comprehensive insights into the entire MSME population in Orange County. more over As with any survey-based research, there is a potential risk of self-reporting bias. Despite taking precautionary measures to minimize this bias, it is essential to consider its potential impact on the accuracy and objectivity of the results. The study's focus on MSMEs registered between 2010 and 2020 provided valuable historical data. However, given the dynamic nature of business environments, the current dynamics and changes in the MSME landscape, particularly considering the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic, might not have been fully captured within this timeframe.

The research explored a variety of financial and non-financial factors that significantly impact MSMEs' success. Nevertheless, the study did not encompass all possible influencing variables, such as cultural aspects and market conditions, which could offer additional depth to the analysis. Acknowledging this limitation will ensure a nuanced interpretation of the findings.

Author Contributions:

Lemuel David

Provided substantial contributions to the interpretation of the results.

Provided critical revisions and intellectual input throughout the writing process.

Assisted with data collection and analysis.

Nosheen Amjad

Revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.

Contributed to the conception and design of the study.

Reviewed and interpreted the data

Meiling Luo 罗美铃

Provided critical revisions and intellectual input throughout the writing process.

Revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, including the data analysis and interpretation

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Provided critical revisions, the methodology, design and intellectual input throughout the writing process.

Approved the final version of the manuscript.

Contributed to the design of the study. Provided critical revisions and intellectual input throughout the writing process. Revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.

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